

Project acronym: EVERSE
 Grant Agreement Number:101129744
 Project full title: European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
 Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

D4.2 Engagement and Software Assessment for Researchers (initial demonstrator of Pilot)

Version: 1.0
 Status: Submitted
 Dissemination Level: Public
 Deliverable Type: DEM
 Due date of deliverable: 31.08.2025
 Actual submission date: 29.08.2025
 Work Package: WP 4: EOSC Science Cluster Pilots and Driver projects
 Lead partner for this deliverable: UvA
 Partner(s) contributing: UNIMAN,HZDR,BSC, CU, ELIXIR, CERTH

Main author(s):

Zhiming Zhao	UvA
--------------	-----

Other author(s):

Caterina Doglioni	UNIMAN
Ondrej Kosarko	CU
Srobona Ghosh	HZDR
Guido Juckeland	HZDR
Salvador Capella	BSC
Pablo Martinez	BSC
Pavel Straňák	CU
Daniel Garijo	UPM
Peter Maccallum	ELIXIR
Fotis Psomopoulos	CERTH
Aspasia Orfanou	CERTH

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
0.1	05.05.2025	Initial draft by UvA	Zhiming Zhao (UvA)
0.6	27.07.2025	First full draft for internal review	Zhiming Zhao (UvA), Caterina Doglioni (UNIMAN)
0.8	08.08.2025	Revisions and feedback	Daniel Garijo (UPM), Pavel Straňák (CU)
0.9	26.08.2025	Feedback incorporated	Salvador Capella (BSC), Ondrej Kosarko (CU), Guido Juckeland (HZDR), Srobona Ghosh (HZDR)
1.0	28.08.2025	Final version	Aspasia Orfanou (CERTH)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 Introduction.....	5
2 Engagement and software assessment in the science clusters.....	6
2.1 ENVRI.....	6
2.1.1 ENVRI Introduction.....	6
2.1.2 ENVRI Progress	7
2.1.3 ENVRI Future Plan	7
2.2 ESCAPE	8
2.2.1 ESCAPE Introduction.....	8
2.2.2 ESCAPE Progress	8
2.2.3 ESCAPE Future Plan	9
2.3 LifeScience RI	9
2.3.1 LifeScience RI Introduction	9
2.3.2 LifeScience RI Progress	9
2.3.3 LifeScience RI Future Plan	10
2.4 PaNOSC.....	10
2.4.1 PaNOSC Introduction	10
2.4.2 PaNOSC Progress	11
2.4.3 PaNOSC Future Plan	12
2.5 SSHOC.....	12
2.5.1 SSHOC Introduction	12
2.5.2 SSHOC Progress	13
2.5.3 SSHOC FuturePlan	13
3 Summary.....	14
4 References	15

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Pilots facilitate the connection between science clusters and RSQKit development. 5

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EVERSE aims to create a framework for research software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities, in pursuit of building a European network for Research Software Quality and setting the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence. To ensure the sustainability of the proposed framework for research software excellence, EVERSE will establish a network amongst the five EOSC Science Clusters (ENVRI-FAIR, LifeScience RI, ESCAPE, PANOSC, and SSHOC), which develop and make research software for their respective European communities (astronomy and accelerator-based physics, life science, photon & neutron science, environmental science, and the social sciences & humanities). In this deliverable, we report the recent progress made by the science clusters on demonstrating the quality model, indicators, and practices of RSQKit in different communities through pilots.

1 Introduction

In the EVERSE project, five science clusters are collaborating closely to review current research software practices within each community and contribute to the development of the RSQKit by engaging the community to test the quality model and indicators and assessing software quality in the community through pilot cases. Feedback will be provided to refine the knowledge base and provide practices to support EVERSE networks, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Pilots facilitate the connection between science clusters and RSQKit development.

Currently, there are five pilots defined in the EVERSE project:

1. **ENVRI (Environmental Sciences):** aims to integrate the EVERSE framework into the ENVRI-HUB Knowledgebase and Virtual Research Environment, and apply to the development of the Essential Climate Variable computing program and cloud workflows;
2. **LifeScience RI (Life Sciences):** the goal of this pilot is to make RO-Crate actionable by incorporating the five safes concept into WfExS for secure and federated workflow orchestration, and use of community-led standards for materialising research software packaged using container technologies and mobilising encrypted data whenever needed;
3. **ESCAPE (Astronomy and particle physics):** aims to deliver ML for scientific data compression (standalone code, Python), a Common Tracking Software, and choose an ATLAS trigger algorithm as an option for the collaboration;
4. **PaNOSC (Photon and neutron science):** Will transition software to high-performance computing (HPC) and heterogeneous computing architectures;
5. **SSHOC (Social sciences):** Aims to develop a multilanguage textual analysis pipeline of tools that use a combination of open-source tools and its own code to create an integrated SotA tool capable of deploying locally or as a service.

In this deliverable, we will provide an overview of the progress of the pilots in the EOSC Science Clusters.

2 Engagement and software assessment in the science clusters

Science clusters have been engaged since the beginning of the project to review current community practices in research software development, quality assessment, and the tools being used. In this section, we will introduce the basic idea, progress, and plan of the pilots.

2.1 ENVRI

2.1.1 ENVRI Introduction

ENVRI is a cluster of research infrastructures from Environmental and Earth sciences. The cluster has been working together via [ENVRI](#), [ENVRIplus](#), [ENVRI-FAIR](#), and [ENVRI-Hub Next projects](#), to develop common vocabularies (ENVRI reference model [1]), to design interoperable data management services, to FAIRify research assets, and to develop an integrated ENVRI hub to enable cross-RI research asset search and use.

The ENVRI community produces different tiers of research software, based on the [categories reviewed by RSQKit](#):

- **Tier one research software (analysis code):** Jupyter notebooks, including Python and R programs used to find, access, and compute data from different RIs.
- **Tier two research software (prototype tools):** the standardized [Essential Climate Variables \(ECV\) workflows](#), which other researchers can reuse as templates or reusable digital objects for composing new workflows.
- **Tier three research software (research software infrastructure):** the framework of the ENVRI-HUB. Currently, the ENVRI-HUB contains four building blocks: 1) a catalogue of services, 2) an ENVRI knowledge base, 3) a training gateway, and 4) an analytics framework. Those components are developed by teams from different institutions following DevOps practices (e.g., CI/CD). Via the project version control system ([GitLab](#)), each software commit is tested, integrated, and deployed via a Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline. Via the analytics framework, researchers can:
 - Develop the tier one research software, e.g., create new ECV workflows
 - Search and reuse the tier two software, e.g., the ECV templates or research objects for making new workflows

In EVERSE, the ENVRI pilot aims to integrate the RSQKit in the ENVRI-HUB framework to achieve the following scenarios:

- A set of performance assessment tools will be provided to guide Tier one research software engineers in assessing and improving their notebook quality.
- DevOps engineers of ENVRI-HUB can conduct a customizable software quality assessment in the CI/CD pipeline to assess and improve the ENVRI-HUB software quality.

The ENVRI team aims to accomplish the goal through the following steps:

1. Collect the existing practices from the ENVRI community and provide them as input to the different task forces for developing the RSQKit and reference model, following the guidelines.

2. Conduct a state-of-the-art survey within ENVRI to review existing software QC practices and tools.
3. Develop a customized ENVRI RS quality model for different tiers of research software.
4. Deliver the customized quality model to the ENVRI community through training activities in conjunction with the RSQKit.
5. Develop a pilot based on the software quality model and tools
6. Improve the software quality model and tools through hackathons or training events.

2.1.2 ENVRI Progress

During the first year of the project, the ENVRI team collaborated with the ENVRI community to review existing practices and contributed to the development of RSQKit. The current version of the [quality model and indicators in RSQKit](#) has been presented to the ENVRI community through various project [meetings and a hackathon](#) jointly organized by ENVRI-HUB and EVERSE. Research software engineers from ENVRI have actively joined the EVERSE network.

The UvA team represents the ENVRI community in the EVERSE project and worked on the following activities for the pilot:

- The quality model provided by RSQKit was reviewed within the context of Jupyter notebooks. A customized quality model has been explicitly proposed for assessing the quality of Jupyter notebooks. The outcome “Socially-Informed Jupyter Notebook Quality: A Role- and Lifecycle-Aware Metrics Framework” [2] has been presented in the 25th conference on software quality, reliability, and security ([QRS 2025](#)).
- Several Jupyter-based quality check tools were tested and integrated into a Jupyter-based Virtual Research Environment (VRE). The work was presented to invited experts for feedback, which was collected to refine the approach.
- Additionally, the RSQKit-recommended quality tools were re-evaluated in the context of CI/CD pipelines. A hackathon was organized within the ENVRI community in collaboration with EVERSE to explore how these tools could be integrated into existing pipelines.
- Investigated how AI-based approaches can enhance the software project quality by detecting Git commit anomalies. The outcome has been presented as a paper, “Unsupervised Detection of Anomalous Commits in Software Repositories” [3] presented at the IEEE Conference on Software Service Engineering ([SSE](#)) 2025.
- A customizable CI/CD pipeline for quality assessment is under development. In the pipeline, different tools developed by the EVERSE technical team, e.g., [resqui](#), will be integrated.

2.1.3 ENVRI Future Plan

In the coming phase of the project, we will:

- Develop customized training material, together with WP5, for RSQKit and the Pilots for the ENVRI community;
- Engage more ENVRI users to test the pilot and scale it out to the broader community, e.g., through training events.

2.2 ESCAPE

2.2.1 ESCAPE Introduction

ESCAPE stands for the European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle Physics ESFRI research infrastructures. This Science Cluster brings together communities and research infrastructures in the areas of astronomy and accelerator-based particle physics, specifically ESFRI facilities (SKAO, CTAO, KM3NeT, EST, ELT, HL-LHC, FAIR) and pan-European research infrastructures (CERN, ESO, JIVE). The objective of ESCAPE is to bring together ESFRI projects with common challenges in terms of data-driven research, with demonstrated expertise in terms of Open Science workflows throughout the entire data lifecycle, to solve fundamental research questions with complementary approaches.

The ESCAPE pilots in EVERSE represent all tiers of research software and are coming from the HL-LHC ESFRI:

- **Tier one research software (analysis code)** based on the *xAODAnaHelpers* framework [4] used by individual researchers to analyse high-throughput data from the Large Hadron Collider;
- **Tier two research software (prototype tools):** *Baler* [5], a **prototype** machine learning **tool** for data compression in high energy physics that is being expanded with different use cases (e.g. computational fluid dynamics);
- **Tier three research software (research software infrastructure):** *A Common Tracking Software (ACTS)*, the **research software infrastructure** for tracking charged particles that is essential for research at the HL-LHC and that a large number of researchers already rely on.

In EVERSE, the ESCAPE pilots aim to demonstrate that improving the software quality has a knock-on effect on research outputs, in terms of both computational resources and human resources. They are also used as well-known examples to connect EVERSE to the relevant initiatives and working groups on software quality in the field, namely the High Energy Physics Software Foundation ([HSE](#)) and the [ICFA Data Lifecycle Panel](#). EVERSE will also integrate and complement the software training available in ESCAPE.

2.2.2 ESCAPE Progress

In this document, we focus on the initial involvement of ESCAPE in EVERSE in terms of pilots, but the cluster also actively contributed to the Virtual Institute (WP1), to the tools and indicators (WP2/WP3) and to Training and Recognition (WP5). During the first year of the project, the engagement of ESCAPE in EVERSE through the pilots has focused on the feedback loop to the RSQKit. The priority so far has been to identify common best practices that are already used in large-scale scientific collaborations such as the experiments at the HL-LHC and map them to those that are common to all Science Clusters within the RSQKit [6], [7]. We have done so through different events that engaged the broader community of the cluster, the researchers responsible for the pilots, and the members of EVERSE, namely:

- [Presentations](#) and Q&A session introducing EVERSE and one of the pilots at the 2024 HEP Software Foundation workshop.
- [Interactive presentation](#) at the HEP Software Foundation workshop in 2025, with feedback from the audience.
- Presentations at the ICFA Data Lifecycle Panel
- Participation in the ICFA Data Lifecycle Panel Editorial Workshop, where we have produced a mapping between the recommendations for software for reproducible open science and RSQKit good practices and between HSF guidelines and RSQKit good

practices. This will be discussed in future RSQKit and WP4 meetings, and these links will be highlighted in the different recommendations/best practices.

One of the ESCAPE members from UofM has also joined the RSQKit Editorial Board and has been and will be including the feedback from these events in the RSQKit.

Work has been ongoing to improve the first two pilots (xAODAnaHelpers [4] and Baler [5]) to include RSQKit practices. To highlight one of the newest efforts in these terms, a new line of research on improving the [environmental sustainability](#) of software is now ongoing for the Baler pilot.

We have also started including other analysis tier pilots in addition to the initial ones around the common theme of dark matter research in the context of the [European Strategy of Particle Physics Update](#).

2.2.3 ESCAPE Future Plan

In the coming phase of the project, we will:

- Engage the developers of the third and most sizable / most used pilot (ACTS) for a code review, defining a pathway towards improvements where the impact on research can also be quantified in terms of metrics;
- Co-organise trainings on RSQKit tasks, tools, and metrics, first for the pilot developers and then for the broader community to join;
- Use the ESCAPE Virtual Research Environment as a platform to run both pilot codes and EVERSE tools and present examples that are “ready to copy” for the broader community.
- Expand to other pilots, linking to funded OSCARS projects within the ESCAPE cluster.

2.3 LifeScience RI

2.3.1 LifeScience RI Introduction

[LifeScience RI](#) integrates the 15 Research Infrastructures related to various life sciences disciplines and applications. This Science cluster is built on the success of EOSC-Life, the EOSC-thematic project funded to promote the organisation of the RIs in the Life Sciences domain and the cross-fertilisation across. Importantly, these RIs do not necessarily focus on the generation and management of research data and research software. Indeed, ELIXIR is one of the primary references for these particular aspects within this Science Cluster. Life Science research integrates a multitude of scientific areas, being conducted by scientists and labs from diverse disciplines. As the approaches used in these disciplines require very transversal competences and technologies involving both heterogeneous services and resource collections, it is common for researchers to use them without making distinctions on what is associated with whom. Indeed, LifeScience RI strives to provide easy access to these services, technologies, and novel approaches for every scientist, aiming to bridge the various technological gaps across its member RIs.

2.3.2 LifeScience RI Progress

During the first year of the project, the LifeScience RI pilot has focused on using [WfExS-backend](#) as a tool to enhance the reproducibility and quality of workflows, while supporting their secure orchestration for sensitive life sciences analyses. WfExS provides mechanisms to fetch workflows from communities like [WorkflowHub](#) and GitHub, as well as to generate and consume [RO-Crates](#), facilitating the consistent materialisation of workflow components and supporting reproducible execution and knowledge transfer. The LifeScience RI team engaged with the community through feedback sessions to assess the applicability of the Five Safes concept and actionable RO-Crates for sensitive data workflows.

The LifeScience RI team carried out the following activities:

- Workflow orchestration testing: WfExS-backend was used to fetch and instantiate workflows from WorkflowHub and GitHub, either via repository URLs or Git endpoints.
- Secure execution validation: Workflows ran in FUSE-encrypted directories protecting sensitive inputs, intermediate results, and outputs. Workflow execution provenance was captured in Workflow Run RO-Crates, which can now be consumed by WfExS to fully reproduce an analysis.
- Output management: Results were securely deposited in either private repositories (Nextcloud, B2DROP) or public repositories (Zenodo, Dataverse), depending on the sensitivity of the data and applicable governance rules.

As WfExS has reached version 1.0.1, the focus is being broadened to highlight components from the ecosystem that enable the analysis of reproducibility and replicability via workflows.

2.3.3 LifeScience RI Future Plan

In the coming phase of the project, we will:

- Explore how RSQKit quality indicators can be applied to workflows themselves, considering that workflows are typically maintained in git repositories and include both source code and metadata.
- Assess how applying RSQKit in this way could support EVERSE's objectives of improving research software quality and enhancing the reproducibility and reliability of workflow-based analyses across communities.
- From an engagement perspective, it is expected to have engagement activities with other members of the LifeScience RI to ensure their practices around software development are considered and eventually incorporated into EVERSE. To channel potential feedback and interest, reproducible and replicable analysis of (sensitive) data would be used as a thematic area to attract interest and generate traction within this Science cluster.

2.4 PaNOSC

2.4.1 PaNOSC Introduction

PaNOSC (Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud) represents a cluster of European research infrastructures specializing in photon and neutron science, encompassing major facilities such as synchrotrons, free-electron lasers, and neutron sources. It unites six ESFRI photon- and neutron-based research infrastructures—ESRF, ILL, ESS, ELI ERIC, European XFEL and CERIC-ERIC—together with national source partners. The cluster has been developing coordinated approaches to data management, analysis workflows, and software development through the PaNOSC and ExPaNDS projects, establishing common data formats, analysis protocols, and interoperable services across participating facilities. The cluster has delivered the NeXus-HDF5 metadata schema, a federated PaN Data Search Portal (OAI-PMH), and the VISA remote analysis platform, thereby enabling cross-facility FAIR data interoperability and petabyte-scale reuse. The cluster also collects relevant research software in its PaN Data Software Catalogue.

The PaNOSC community generates research software spanning multiple complexity tiers, aligned with the RSQKit categorization framework:

- **Tier one research software (analysis code):** Tier one research software encompasses experimental control scripts, data reduction notebooks, and analysis workflows typically developed by beamline scientists and users. These include Python-based on-instrument Jupyter notebooks for real-time data analysis, instrument control interfaces, EPICS beamline scripts and real-time data reduction macros, and specialized visualization tools for diffraction patterns, spectroscopy data, and imaging datasets. The software often integrates with facility-specific detector systems and beamline hardware, requiring robust error handling and performance optimization for large-scale data processing. Due to this internal usage and the customization to fit a very specific technical setup, these types of software are usually not made public and are only shared in direct collaborations with other facilities.
- **Tier two research software (prototype tools):** Tier two research software includes standardized analysis pipelines and reusable workflow templates that can be adapted across different experimental techniques and facilities. Examples include tomographic reconstruction algorithms, e.g. tomver [8], crystallographic refinement workflows, e.g. [CrystFEL](#), and time-resolved spectroscopy analysis chains, e.g., [demeter](#). These tools are designed for reproducibility and cross-facility compatibility, often incorporating containerization and workflow management systems like Nextflow (workflow manager) or Snakemake to ensure consistent execution environments.
- **Tier three research software (research software infrastructure):** Tier three research software comprises the foundational infrastructure supporting the PaNOSC ecosystem, including the [Open Data Portal](#), distributed computing frameworks, and data catalog services. The architecture follows microservices (OpenStack + Kubernetes) principles with containerized deployments managed through Kubernetes orchestration. Development teams across multiple institutions collaborate using GitLab-based version control with automated testing, security scanning, and deployment pipelines. The system supports federated authentication, metadata standardization through NeXus formats, and scalable data processing capabilities for petabyte-scale experimental datasets. It also encompasses PaN Data Search APIs and federated AAI via UmbrellaID.

In EVERSE, the PaNOSC pilot focuses both on documenting generic lessons around automated testing for high-performance computing and programming for heterogeneous architectures in RSQKit as well as integrating RSQKit methodologies into existing development workflows to address specific challenges in photon and neutron science software development. The implementation strategy follows a multi-phase approach where RSQKit components are systematically integrated into existing PaNOSC infrastructure. Initial phases focus on establishing quality baselines through comprehensive software audits across participating facilities. Subsequent phases involve deploying automated assessment tools and training facility staff on quality-driven development practices. The final phase emphasizes community adoption through demonstration projects and best practice dissemination.

2.4.2 PaNOSC Progress

During the initial project phase, the PaNOSC cluster has made contributions to RSQKit development while establishing pilot infrastructure within the photon and neutron science community. Facility representatives from major European installations have actively participated in EVERSE workshops, contributing domain-specific requirements and validation of proposed quality models.

The PaNOSC cluster has conducted an initial software landscape analysis across participating facilities using one of its [workgroup meetings](#), identifying common patterns in experimental software development and deployment practices. This analysis revealed significant variation in quality assurance approaches between facilities, highlighting the need for standardized yet flexible quality assessment frameworks that can accommodate diverse experimental environments and software architectures.

As part of the PaNOSC pilot, two specific software packages ([alpaka](#) and [PiConGPU](#)) are contributed as code examples. The TechRadar tools were run for both software packages and aggregated in internal reports.

Furthermore, the [PaN-Training](#) portal and the previously mentioned work groups were harvested for training material for research software engineering used in the science cluster. This information has been aggregated in an internal collection that can be referenced from RSQkit pages as applicable.

2.4.3 PaNOSC Future Plan

The next phase of the PaNOSC pilot development will focus on broadening the interactions into the whole science cluster. This will be accomplished via the already established relationships with the information technology working groups from LEAPS and LENS as well as via the newly established OSCARS competence center for PaNOSC.

The goal is to host multiple workshops on integrating good practice tools promoted by EVERSE into the software development environments for the various PaNOSC software packages. This will also generate more feedback on the applicability of the proposed tools and will also build a list of software repositories to watch and maybe even automatically check for future identified good practices.

Additionally, the same group of experts will be consulted on refining and potentially establishing a science cluster-specific RSE training curriculum using the identified training resources.

2.5 SSHOC

2.5.1 SSHOC Introduction

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster (SSH Open Cluster) brings together a diverse range of researchers and research infrastructures (RIs) working across various domains, including linguistics, history, cultural heritage, political science, and digital humanities. The cluster builds upon the achievements of the SSHOC project, which fostered collaboration across six key European RIs: [CESSDA](#), [ESS Survey](#), [DARIAH](#), [CLARIN](#), [SHARE](#), [E-RIHS](#). The SSH Open Cluster focuses on supporting research through bespoke software tools and services that address the specific needs and practices of the SSH disciplines.

In the SSH domain, software tools are often distributed in parallel with data, functioning as "data packages" with rich metadata and documentation. These tools are accessed and reused in various ways—through APIs for programmatic workflows or through user-friendly interfaces designed for researchers with limited technical backgrounds. Language-related technologies, including tools for speech recognition, text processing, and multimodal analysis, play a particularly critical role and are frequently driven by machine learning models trained on SSH data.

The SSH Open Cluster pilot in EVERSE focuses on UDPipe, a widely used suite of natural language processing tools. The pilot traces the path of UDPipe from a research prototype to a production-ready, infrastructure-level software solution. This evolution includes

containerisation, web-service deployment, and scalability for high-volume data processing, all while maintaining accessibility for non-programming users in the digital humanities and arts.

In EVERSE, we aim to map a path from research prototype to robust, reusable research infrastructure software by employing relevant recommendations and tooling from the RSQKit.

2.5.2 SSHOC Progress

In the first phase, the team has engaged in several activities:

1. Contributed to and reviewed the RSQKit.
2. Participated in multiple questionnaires and workshops, helping uncover SSH-specific workflows and practices with the RSQKit indicators and models;
3. Presented the UDPipe pilot as a use case.
4. Began identifying touchpoints between existing community-developed training materials and the new training opportunities developed under EVERSE.

2.5.3 SSHOC Future Plan

Looking ahead, we will:

1. Expand user engagement across SSHOC-related RIs by introducing EVERSE and RSQKit at targeted community events, such as conference "bazaar" sessions or tool showcases;
2. Gather feedback on RSQKit through direct user interaction
3. Further develop the UDPipe pilot by refining containerisation, with attention to performance, sustainability, and ease of use;
4. Explore integration pathways between EVERSE training resources (e.g., everse-training.app.cern.ch) and SSH-specific learning platforms such as the Training Toolkit (training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu);

3 Summary

This deliverable summarizes the current status of the pilots in the EVERSE project. The development of RSQKit is still in progress; the latest release has already been integrated into various training sessions and hackathons across different scientific communities. Moving forward, clusters will continue to contribute to RSQKit's development with a focus on user engagement. This includes customizing RSQKit to address the specific needs of different science clusters and integrating it into the existing practices of the research software engineering community.

4 References

- [1] A. N. De La Hidalga, A. Hardisty, P. Martin, B. Magagna, and Z. Zhao, “The ENVRI Reference Model,” in *Towards Interoperable Research Infrastructures for Environmental and Earth Sciences*, vol. 12003, Z. Zhao and M. Hellström, Eds., in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 12003. , Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 61–81. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-52829-4_4.
- [2] A. Volentir, N. Soveizi, and Z. Zhao, “Socially-Informed Jupyter Notebook Quality: A Role- and Lifecycle-Aware Metrics Framework,” presented at the International Workshop on Human and Social Aspects of Software Quality (HASQ 2025), Hangzhou, China.
- [3] N. Soveizi, T. Candeias, M. Zivkovic, and Z. Zhao, “Unsupervised Detection of Anomalous Commits in Software Repositories,” in *2025 IEEE International Conference on Software Services Engineering (SSE)*, Helsinki, Finland: IEEE, Jul. 2025, pp. 31–38. doi: 10.1109/SSE67621.2025.00013.
- [4] G. Stark et al., *xAODAnaHelpers*, v1.0.0. (Nov. 18, 2022). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.7335128.
- [5] Alexander Ekman et al., *baler-collaboration/baler: Blocked and Error Bound Training*. (Feb. 28, 2024). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10723669.
- [6] E. Breitmoser, “Milestone 8 (extended version): First evaluation of the tools and services in the form of a workshop against WP2 initial best practices (MS4) and recommendations to adapt these tools if necessary.,” May 2025, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.15487981.
- [7] K. Graf and J. Schnabel, “WP2 MS4 Initial best practices landscaping results,” Jul. 2025, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.16569797.
- [8] H. Payno et al., *tomwer*. (May 22, 2025). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.15746751.